

BLADE: Better Language Answers through Dialogue and Explanations

Chathuri Jayaweera and Bonnie J. Dorr
University of Florida
{chathuri.jayawee, bonniejdorr}@ufl.edu

Abstract

Large language model (LLM)-based educational assistants often provide direct answers that short-circuit learning by reducing exploration, self-explanation, and engagement with course materials. We present BLADE (Better Language Answers through Dialogue and Explanations), a grounded conversational assistant that guides learners to relevant instructional resources rather than supplying immediate solutions. BLADE uses a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) framework over curated course content, dynamically surfacing pedagogically relevant excerpts in response to student queries. Instead of delivering final answers, BLADE prompts direct engagement with source materials to support conceptual understanding. We conduct an impact study in an undergraduate computer science course, with different course resource configurations and show that BLADE improves students' navigation of course resources and conceptual performance compared to simply providing the full inventory of course resources. These results demonstrate the potential of grounded conversational AI to reinforce active learning and evidence-based reasoning.

1 Introduction

The rapid expansion of digital learning resources has created a paradox in higher education: while students now have unprecedented access to instructional materials, they often struggle to identify the specific content that bridges a question to genuine conceptual understanding. Textbooks, lecture slides, recorded lectures, and curated readings are typically distributed across multiple platforms, leaving learners to manually search for relevant information with limited guidance.

Recent advances in large language models (LLMs) have driven widespread adoption of conversational assistants for educational support. However, most existing systems prioritize direct answer generation, which can short-circuit effective

learning by reducing opportunities for exploration, self-explanation, and sustained engagement with instructional resources. Prior work in learning sciences emphasizes the importance of active inquiry, evidence-based reasoning, and interaction with authoritative materials for durable conceptual understanding. At the same time, overreliance on AI-generated responses raises concerns about passive learning, misplaced trust, and reduced verification behavior, particularly in the presence of hallucinated or oversimplified outputs.

Figure 1: The BLADE interaction paradigm, in which a curriculum-aware conversational assistant retrieves and highlights relevant instructional resources in response to student queries. Instead of supplying final answers, BLADE directs learners to evidence within course materials, supporting explanation-centered learning and active resource exploration.

To address these limitations, we introduce BLADE (Better Language Answers through Dialogue and Explanations), an implemented and empirically evaluated conversational assistant designed to guide learners toward relevant instructional resources rather than supplying immediate solutions. BLADE anchors interaction in curated course materials—including textbooks, lecture slides, readings, and annotated resources—intentionally shifting the focus from an-

answer delivery to guided resource discovery (Figure 1). Rather than synthesizing final responses, BLADE retrieves and highlights pedagogically relevant segments of course content, encouraging learners to consult authoritative sources and construct their own conceptual understanding through evidence-based exploration.

Our contributions are 1) a learning-oriented system that guides students to authoritative, curriculum-aligned passages and uses those materials as the foundation for conversational interaction, and 2) an impact study to determine the effectiveness of BLADE in an undergraduate course where the student usage of resources and their performance are analyzed under three configurations of resource allocation.

By anchoring each exchange in vetted instructional content, BLADE provides transparent evidence for its guidance, reducing the risk of misinformation and hallucination. This design encourages active learning behaviors—including elaboration, self-explanation, and retrieval practice—by prompting learners to engage directly with source material, which prior work has shown to support long-term retention and conceptual transfer. In so doing, BLADE combines the natural fluency of dialogue with verifiable, traceable references, improving both learning outcomes and the transparency of AI-assisted support.

In this paper, we present the design, implementation, and classroom evaluation of BLADE within an undergraduate computer science course. Our results demonstrate that students using BLADE more effectively locate relevant resources and achieve higher conceptual performance compared to students relying on materials alone. Experiments done on evaluating the impact of BLADE in student performance show that, while BLADE access alone does not significantly improve student performance, the combination of BLADE with access to course materials improves both students’ aggregate exam scores and their question-level accuracy (i.e., the proportion of correct responses).

2 Related Work

The intersection of retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) and education has attracted increasing attention as researchers seek to combine the factual reliability of information retrieval with the expressive flexibility of large language models. Early work on knowledge-grounded dialogue systems, such

as the incorporation of external document stores into conversational agents (Lewis et al., 2020), demonstrates that grounding responses in retrieved text markedly reduces hallucination compared with purely generative models. Subsequent extensions have applied this principle to instructional settings, where systems retrieve textbook passages or lecture notes to support answer generation (Henkel et al., 2024; Li et al., 2025). These studies highlight the pedagogical benefit of exposing learners to source material, yet they often allowed the model to synthesize a direct answer that incorporated the retrieved evidence.

A parallel line of research has explored “answer-avoidance” or “prompt-only” tutoring bots that intentionally withhold explicit solutions. Approaches rooted in Socratic questioning (Alshaikh et al., 2020) or scaffolded hint generation (Rivers and Koedinger, 2014) aim to provoke deeper reasoning by prompting students to locate and apply concepts themselves. However, many of these systems rely on handcrafted rule-based hints or limited knowledge bases, which restrict scalability across subjects and course offerings.

More recent RAG-based tutoring prototypes have begun to merge these strands. Retrieval-augmented generation in knowledge-intensive QA (Lewis et al., 2020) has popularized hybrid retriever-generator architectures that condition concise explanations on short evidence snippets, explicitly encouraging users to inspect the cited passages. Similarly, recent RAG-based learning-assistant frameworks for education (Li et al., 2025) format responses with explicit citations to retrieved resources, yet typically still default to providing a direct answer when a high-confidence snippet is found.

The educational technology literature also offers insights into the cognitive advantages of resource-directed feedback. Constructivist learning theory (Piaget, 1973), and the concept of “learning by retrieval” (Roediger and Butler, 2011) argue that prompting learners to search for and interpret information promotes stronger memory traces than passive receipt of facts. Empirical studies on guided discovery tools in computer science education (Kelleher et al., 2007) report improved problem-solving transfer when students are required to locate relevant documentation rather than being handed the solution.

Collectively, these bodies of work suggest three unresolved challenges that motivate the present

study. First, most RAG tutoring systems still prioritize answer delivery, leaving a gap for assistants that consistently defer to the source material. Second, the retrieval component is rarely fine-tuned to the pedagogical relevance of snippets—relevance in an educational sense is not synonymous with topical similarity alone. Third, there is limited empirical evidence on how a strictly “resource-pointing” conversational agent affects learning outcomes within a real classroom context.

Our contributions build on retrieval-grounded architectures (Lewis et al., 2020) by introducing a curriculum-aware indexing pipeline, a contrastive retriever trained on instructional relevance, and a generation schema that explicitly refrains from answering while foregrounding the most pedagogically useful passages. By evaluating this system in an undergraduate computer-science course, we aim to close the loop between the technical advances in RAG and the educational imperative of fostering autonomous, evidence-based learning.

3 BLADE System Architecture

BLADE is built on a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) framework that integrates curriculum-specific content with a conversational LLM interface. The system consists of three primary components: (i) a curriculum-aware content repository, (ii) an instructional relevance retriever, and (iii) a controllable generation module designed to foreground evidence rather than direct answers.

3.1 Curriculum-Aware Content Indexing

Course materials—including textbooks, lecture slides, readings, and supplementary documents—are segmented into semantically coherent instructional units. These units are annotated with metadata such as topic alignment, learning objectives, and instructional context (e.g., lecture or textbook chapter). This structured indexing enables fine-grained retrieval of pedagogically relevant content in response to learner queries.

3.2 Instructional Relevance Retrieval

Unlike standard information retrieval systems optimized solely for topical similarity, BLADE’s retriever is trained to prioritize instructional usefulness. Using contrastive learning objectives, the retriever learns to rank content fragments based on their ability to support conceptual understanding, rather than keyword overlap alone. This allows

Figure 2: An example of a typical BLADE response to a query with citations of sources. The cited sources include textbook/course material excerpts as well as lecture transcripts with timestamps of the relevant portion.

the system to surface passages that best scaffold student learning.

Figure 2 shows an interaction with BLADE where the generated response for the student’s query on a course concept (e.g., Jaccard Similarity) is grounded in both course material, such as Project notebooks and lecture transcripts. The citations also point to the relevant timestamps in a lecture transcript, so that relevant information is easily located.

3.3 Evidence-Focused Dialogue Generation

The generative component of BLADE is explicitly constrained to avoid providing final answers. Instead, it produces conversational prompts that reference retrieved instructional content, encourage exploration of highlighted passages, and suggest follow-up reading where appropriate. This design promotes learner engagement with original materials while maintaining a supportive dialogue.

4 Classroom Deployment and Evaluation

BLADE is deployed and has now been assessed in an impact study in fall 2025 in an undergrad-

uate computer science course focused on natural language processing. Students are allowed to interact with the assistant alongside standard course materials during homework assignments and study sessions.

The BLADE impact study involves 85 undergraduate computer science students enrolled in a course, recruited via a study announcement and interest form. After recruitment, students are randomly divided into three groups and assigned three quizzes on NLP concepts spanning three course modules. Each group completes the quizzes under three different resource configurations, resulting in a total of nine assignments.

BLADE is evaluated along three primary dimensions: (i) learners’ ability to locate relevant instructional resources, (ii) conceptual understanding as measured by assessments aligned with course objectives, and (iii) self-reported confidence in navigating course content independently.

The results indicate that students using BLADE exhibit improved resource discovery, increased consultation of authoritative sources, and higher conceptual performance relative to control groups using traditional materials. Survey results further suggest that BLADE supports learners’ ability to identify relevant content without direct answers.

4.1 Resource Configurations

Students complete the quizzes in a controlled environment where they could access only the assigned resources during the quiz. After completing each quiz, students provide feedback on their use of assigned resources through a survey. In addition, student performance on each quiz is analyzed.

4.2 Group Assignments

The resource configurations used during quiz completion are presented here:

- Config A: Quiz with access to BLADE but no other course resources.
- Config B: Quiz with access to BLADE plus all course resources.
- Config C: Quiz with no access to BLADE, but access to other course resources.

The student group assignment across quizzes and configurations (nine total assignments) are shown here:

Quiz	Config A	Config B	Config C
Quiz 1	group1	group2	group3
Quiz 2	group2	group3	group1
Quiz 3	group3	group1	group2

5 Results

Students are considered in three performance groups based on their overall score for each quiz:

- **Upper:** 27% of students
- **Mid:** 46% of students
- **Lower:** 46% of students

5.1 Correct Answer Selection and Overall Performance

We analyze the distribution of students who pick the correct answer to a question in the three quizzes, normalized by the total number of students who take the quiz, for:

- Upper-performance students
- Mid-performance students
- Lower-performance students
- All students (overall)

As illustrated by the distributions for students in the upper-, mid-, and lower-performance groups, and the overall study participants (Figures 3, 4, and 5), the highest average proportion of students who pick correct answers occurs when learners have access to both BLADE and the course materials. For the upper-performance cohort, use of BLADE alone shows a modest improvement over the condition in which only the course materials are available.

Figure 3: Distribution of upper-performance who picked the correct answer in each quiz, normalized by the total number of quiz-takers.

Figure 4: Distribution of lower-performance students who picked the correct answer in each quiz, normalized by the total number of quiz-takers.

Figure 6: Distribution of mid-performance students who picked the correct answer in each quiz, normalized by the total number of quiz-takers.

Figure 5: Distribution of all students who picked the correct answer in each quiz, normalized by the total number of quiz-takers.

Figure 7: Distribution of the scores of the students as a percentage for the three resource allocations.

By contrast, mid-performance students appear to benefit most when provided with course materials (Figure 6). The distributions of student scores for assigned quizzes with the designated resource configuration (Figure 7) also show the highest average score when BLADE was provided with course materials, suggesting BLADE’s usefulness in guiding students to relevant resources.

Similarly, the distributions of difficulty indices for quiz questions, calculated from student performance across the three resource settings, follow the same pattern (Figure 8). While a higher difficulty index suggests that a question is easy, a lower difficulty index indicates that the question is poorly worded, misleading, or difficult. However, because the questions are the same for all students, the observed variations in the difficulty-index distributions can be attributed to differences in resource allocation. The higher average difficulty index for the BLADE and course material combination indicates that, in this resource setting, students are more likely to answer quiz questions correctly.

5.2 The usage of provided resources

Figure 9 shows the percentage of students who use the provided resources to answer at least one quiz question under each resource allocation. A considerable percentage of students have not used the provided resources and have relied on their own knowledge across all three resource settings.

However, this tendency is highest in settings where only course materials were accessible to students and lowest in the combined BLADE-and-course-materials condition. This suggests that simply providing course materials does not prompt students to consult them during graded assignments, likely due to the time required to locate relevant portions of the material.

This observation is further supported by higher percentages of students who used BLADE alone or in combination with the course materials, while only a very small percentage of students have used only the course material, even when BLADE is available, suggesting that BLADE’s ability to identify relevant areas of the course materials is preferred by students.

Figure 8: Distribution of the difficulty indices of the quiz questions according to student performance with the three resource allocations.

6 Conclusions

BLADE introduces a curriculum-aware, explanation-centered framework for supporting human learning through structured interaction with large language models. By integrating instructional content repositories with relevance-driven retrieval and evidence-focused generation, BLADE enables learners to receive responses grounded in course-specific materials rather than generic model knowledge. The system emphasizes transparency and pedagogical alignment, providing not only answers but also contextualized explanations tied directly to instructional resources.

Empirical deployments demonstrate that BLADE could improve learners’ engagement with domain content, encourage exploration of supporting materials, and foster deeper conceptual understanding through dialogue-based interaction. Rather than functioning as a traditional intelligent tutoring system, BLADE serves as an interactive learning companion, guiding students toward evidence-backed reasoning while maintaining flexibility for open-ended inquiry.

The student performance analysis indicates improved outcomes when both BLADE and course materials are available, with reduced question difficulty in this condition, highlighting BLADE’s effectiveness as an assistive tool for locating relevant source materials. Resource usage analysis further indicates greater reliance on course materials when BLADE is present compared to when course materials are provided alone.

Overall, BLADE establishes the feasibility and value of combining large language models with structured educational resources to support explanation-driven learning, laying a foundation for subsequent systems that more deeply integrate

human–AI interaction into authentic task contexts.

7 Future Work

Building on the foundational capabilities of BLADE, several directions naturally emerge for advancing human-centered AI learning systems.

One avenue for further evaluation of BLADE’s long-term effectiveness is to assess whether it enhances students’ retention of learned concepts compared to traditional course resources alone, using pre- and post-assessments of student performance.

Furthermore, a key opportunity lies in embedding AI interaction directly within authentic task environments, allowing learners to engage with AI assistance while actively completing domain-specific assignments, analyses, or decision-making tasks. Such integration would enable richer observation of how AI influences real-world reasoning processes beyond isolated explanation dialogues.

Future systems should also incorporate comprehensive behavioral instrumentation, capturing not only AI dialogue content but also users’ navigation of resources, verification strategies, timing of actions, and revision behaviors. These multimodal interaction traces would support fine-grained measurement of reliance, skepticism, and self-correction—core components of effective human–AI collaboration.

Finally, expanding beyond single-domain curricular settings to support multiple disciplines—such as medicine, social sciences, and humanities—would enable broader evaluation of explanation-centered AI assistance across varied reasoning contexts.

Together, these directions point toward a new generation of interactive AI learning environments that extend BLADE’s curriculum-aware foundations into richer, measurable, and cognitively resilient human-AI systems.

8 Limitations

Despite its strengths, BLADE exhibits key limitations that constrain its ability to support broader cognitive training and rigorous behavioral analysis.

First, BLADE is primarily designed for constrained, explanation-centered learning scenarios within specific curricular domains, particularly natural language processing. While effective for structured concept exploration, it does not fully integrate AI interaction into authentic task execution (e.g., writing reports, solving domain-specific problems,

Resource-use distribution for three groups

Figure 9: The percentage of students in each resource configuration who used the designated resources to answer at least one question

or making real-time decisions). As a result, user engagement with BLADE occurs largely in isolation from real task performance, limiting insight into how AI assistance influences applied reasoning.

Second, although BLADE encourages users to consult instructional materials through evidence-focused responses, it does not systematically instrument or log fine-grained user behaviors. The system lacks continuous measurement of interaction sequences such as resource access patterns, verification behaviors, follow-up questioning strategies, or timing information. This restricts the ability to quantitatively assess reliance on AI outputs, depth of verification, or self-correction over time.

Finally, BLADE operates largely as a standalone instructional assistant rather than as part of a broader experimental framework capable of supporting staged learning, longitudinal evaluation, or comparisons across varied interaction conditions.

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